

THE CHARACTERISTICS OF FOLKLORE IN THE LITERARY USAGE

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Abstract. *The corpus of folklore literature occupies a distinct position within the longstanding framework of cultural and spiritual values that characterize our society. These works captivate audiences through their artistic representation of customs, emotional experiences, and diverse religious perspectives that have persisted as traditions since antiquity. The following article investigates the features of folklore in the context of literary usage.*

Key words: *folk, literature, oral, art, fairy tale, bakhshi.*

Folklore constitutes both the inception and conclusion of any artistic endeavor, thereby establishing a profound synergy with various other art forms while simultaneously representing a distinct category of art. This domain encompasses concepts associated with music, dance, craftsmanship, fine arts, and a multitude of other artistic expressions. In a more comprehensive sense, oral creativity embodies a generative process that encapsulates the historical, contemporary, and prospective narratives of a culture, intricately intertwined with its fate. Consequently, scholars have designated this phenomenon as folk literature. To ascertain the essence of a community, one must initially investigate their folklore [1]. Folk art epitomizes an art form characterized by perpetual transformation and dynamic evolution in its truest sense. Folk art is indicative of an ongoing transformation, a continual dynamism in the most authentic interpretation of the term. This implies that manifestations of folk art are in a constant state of renewal, alteration, and enhancement, all the while safeguarding the continuity of traditions within each rendition. This phenomenon elucidates the existence of multifarious variations within folk art examples. Such variability is among the most critical dimensions that affirm the distinctiveness of folk art. A hallmark of folk art is its oral performance, which is not only orally mastered but also orally transmitted, orally executed, and orally inherited; in essence, it is recreated through each performance. Folklorists assert that within the realm of folklore, there exists not merely a song, but rather a state of performance—the act of executing a song. This concept is applicable across other genres of folk art. Oral artistry is encapsulated by the terminologies "folklore" or "folk oral poetry." The term

"folklore" was first introduced in 1846 by William Thomas, a researcher from the 19th century [2]. A fairy tale stands as one of the principal genres within folklore, exemplifying artistic prose within this domain. Fairy tales emerged from the captivating narratives recounted by folk artists concerning life, daily experiences, adventures, and, on occasion, societal events.

Fundamentally, folklore is perceived as encompassing all artistic manifestations produced by the populace—architecture, painting, jewelry, gold embroidery, music, dance, and oral literature [1]. Each expert engaged in the artistic realm designates their selected genre as "folklore." For instance, a musician identifies folk melodies, a choreographer recognizes folk dances, an architect acknowledges folk architecture, while a folklorist pertains to folk epics and fairy tales as creations of folklore. In antiquity, Uzbek folk oral poetry was referred to as "folk literature," "oral literature," or "folk oral art." The term "folklore" was initially employed by Khodi Zarifov during the years 1934-35 and subsequently gained prominence under the designation "Uzbek folklore." Works of Uzbek folk oral poetry exemplify the spoken word, encompassing a diverse array of genres that artistically mirror the life, history, aspirations, and worldview of the people, being performed and transmitted orally from generation to generation.

Folklore is fundamentally oral and encompasses components characteristic of all forms of artistic expression, wherein verbal language, melodies, and musical compositions are executed in conjunction with dance. The existence, historical narrative, and destiny of a community are artistically encapsulated within folklore. The foundation of folklore artifacts gradually crystallizes within the worldviews of individuals, evolving from rudimentary mythological constructs to sophisticated religious convictions. Folklore artifacts, as a manifestation of verbal artistry, exhibit numerous distinguishing traits that set them apart from analogous instances of written literature and other artistic modalities [3]. Primarily, these attributes of folklore are rooted in its collective generativity, and thus folklore is predicated upon several fundamental principles.

Community - the oral poetry of the Uzbek folk tradition is generated by the populace. However, this collectivism does not preclude the potential for individual artistic expression; rather, it embraces individual creativity as an essential prerequisite. In nature, one can observe streams comprising droplets and rivers formed by streams, yet it is inconceivable to extricate a singular droplet or stream

from a river and designate it as belonging to a specific stream, analogous to the difficulty in isolating a stanza or segment from a traditional folk song, epic, or fairy tale, and attributing it to a singular creator. Nevertheless, the presence of such an artist is indisputable. Given that instances of folk artistry emerge from a collective creative process, the principal character or "I" within these works exhibits a notable divergence in essence when compared to protagonists in written and oral literature.

The protagonist of folklore corresponds to the collective "I" that has attained a generalized condition, representing the populace at large. As societal conditions evolve, along with socio-political dynamics and the transition of human cognition from mythological paradigms to mythopoetic and artistic-aesthetic frameworks, individual performers—singers, storytellers, bakhshi, enthusiasts, and other creators, as well as educational institutions, instructors, and student rapport—have emerged [1]. Individuals distinguished by exceptional talent in the performing arts include Tilla kampir, Sulton kampir, Jalmon baxshi, Buron shoir, Jumanbulbul, Jassoq shoir, Khonimjon Khalfa, Bibishoira, Suyavbakhshi, Aminshoir, Yo‘ldoshbulbul, Sultonmurod, Qurbonbek, Khidirshoir, Yo‘ldosh shoir, Suyar shoir, Shema yuzboshi, Mulla Xolnazar, Haybat soqi, Qunduz soqi, Ergash Jumanbulbul o‘g‘li, Fozil Yo‘ldosh o‘g‘li, Po‘lkan Jonmurod o‘gli, Islom Nazar o‘g‘li, Nurmon Abdivoy o‘g‘li, Saidmurod Panoh o‘gli, Abdulla shoir, Umir shoir, Kholyor Abdukarim o‘g‘li, Bolabakhshi, Rahmatulla Yusuf o‘g‘li, Qodir Rahim o‘g‘li, among others. Due to the exceptional skills, talents, and endeavors of such creative individuals, the works birthed from the collective ingenuity have been transmitted across generations, refined, and have ascended to a distinguished artistic caliber, thereby establishing classical instances of folklore as a communal heritage.

Anonymity is defined by the ambiguity surrounding the authorship of folklore compositions - anonymity (derived from the Greek term Anonymis - unknown). Folklore is devoid of a singular authorial figure. Regardless of whether one is considering a folk epic, a fairy tale, or a ritualistic song, the genesis, as well as the creator and temporal context of these works, remains ambiguous. As each piece is transmitted across generations, it is susceptible to modifications that reflect the exigencies of time; however, its foundational elements and traditions remain steadfast. An individual may indeed conceive a work within the realm of folklore, but if the narrative, visual elements, and melodic techniques of this creation are rooted in the traditions of folk art, it is subsequently classified as a folklore piece. Over time, it

is further shaped by folk performers, evolving into a quintessential example of folklore.

Orality constitutes a fundamental aspect of the existence and creativity inherent in folk art. Folklore emerges from the repository of collective folk memory, stemming from the oral conveyance of recollections across generations, transmitted from one individual to another. In this context, the foundational element comprises shared folklore knowledge and traditions. The source of memory and folklore knowledge is not attributable to a single individual or a select few, but rather encompasses the collective knowledge and traditions of an entire community. This knowledge and these traditions are perpetuated through the mentorship of educators to learners, traversing generations and evolving within the spirit of contemporary society, enriched by the contributions of new performers and creators. Such refinement entails the incorporation of alterations in the form and content of a specific folklore piece, whether through the addition or omission of elements. For instance, a historical detail may be excluded from a work due to the lapse of memory. Conversely, if the amnesia regarding the musical segment of an epic facilitates its survival in the guise of a fairy tale, then a new epic may emerge, thanks to the interpretation of a skilled artist, drawing upon the narrative of the fairy tale and adopting the form of a tradition. These instances exemplify the characteristic traits of folklore as a dynamic process of oral expression. Indeed, folklore thrives through oral transmission, whereas literature is disseminated through written text. Folklore is conveyed orally and performed vocally, while literature is exclusively encountered through reading.

Traditionalism constitutes a paramount characteristic of folklore, offering a distinctive lifestyle, aesthetic, and modes of expression. Folklore is fundamentally understood as the artistry of traditions. Traditionalism encompasses not merely the relative permanence of the textual and performative methodologies associated with a specific work during the oral transmission process, but also signifies that the attributes of the initial rendition of this work have largely persisted unaltered throughout its transference across generations. Traditionalism emerges as a manifestation of collaborative creativity and a way of life, simultaneously serving as an exceptional form and mechanism for the communal preservation of folklore. Oral expression functions as both a mode of executing folklore and a lifestyle, demanding from the performer substantial memory capabilities, recitation skills, memorization, and pre-established forms and expressions appropriate to the context. In this regard,

traditionalism in folklore represents the most accessible and dependable source of influence. Variability and versioning entail that each rendition of folklore samples constitutes a distinct iteration. A folklore piece is reconstituted during the performance, transitioning into a novel state of existence, which in turn engenders its unique version. Therefore, folklore exists in diverse iterations throughout the performance.

Variability embodies the essence of folklore's existence. This trait characterizes the inherent nature of folklore, its creation, the principles governing life in dynamic oral creativity, and comprehensively encompasses the narrative, figurative, poetic, and genre-specific attributes of folklore works. A variant is defined as an alternate rendition of a particular work that emerges within the context of a living oral epic tradition, capable of existing concurrently without negating one another. The variant retains the overarching narrative of the work, the sequence of motifs, and the actions of the characters; however, there may be specific divergences in their interpretation, description, and forms of expression. Depending on contextual factors, the artist may choose to elaborate on a specific motif, deliver it in a condensed manner, or entirely omit it.

Folklorist William Bascom (1965) delineates four functions of folklore, which concurrently operate within familial folklore groups. He posited that folklore serves to entertain, reinforce cultural identity, educate, and sustain social cohesion. All folktales originated as orally transmitted narratives. Each tale typically conveys a moral or lesson. Numerous ancient folktales elucidate the origins of particular phenomena. Folktales predominantly feature either animals or human characters. Generally, the protagonist of a folktale is confronted with an insurmountable challenge. The term folklore encompasses traditional beliefs, narratives, customs, and stories that are orally transmitted across generations.

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